

DELIVERABLE D8.1

Communication plan

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PU: Public	X
CO: Confidential, only for members for the consortium	

Deliverable type	(X)
R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	X
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DIS: Websites, patents, filing, press and media actions, videos, etc	
OTHER: Software, technical diagram	
ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot	

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CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION AND SUMMARY.....	4
2	DISSEMINATION PROCEDURE	4
2.1	General rule	4
2.2	Procedure for partners: scientific publication or patent	5
3	Communication plan.....	6
3.1	Project needs definition.....	6
3.2	Stakeholder identification.....	7
3.3	Project identity	7
3.4	Main communication channels.....	8
4	ONLINE CHANNELS.....	9
4.1	Conferences, invited seminars and workshops	11
4.2	Technical and demonstration workshops	12
4.3	Journal publications.....	12
5	MONITORING AND EVALUATION PLAN	13
6	ALLOCATED RESOURCES	14

1 INTRODUCTION AND SUMMARY

The external communication and dissemination plan aims at precisising the type of activities and variety of audiences to maximize the promotion of ICARUS and its impact.

This plan identifies the information needs of the specific project stakeholders and determines channels for tailored, target-specific communications and dissemination activities. In accordance with the glossary of terms “communication” and “dissemination” available on the EC Europa Website, this plan contains:

- 📄 Appropriate means to publicly disclose the results - other than protecting or exploiting them. e.g., scientific publications (dissemination)
- 📄 Strategic and targeted measures to communicate about the action and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange (communication).

Thus, the external communication and dissemination plan consists of a strategic plan for the use and dissemination of results of the ICARUS project. Results refer to any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature. It is structured in two parts:

- 📄 Description of the dissemination procedure
- 📄 Presentation of the communication plan

This plan ensures that ICARUS partners will provide the knowledge gained during the project’s lifetime in the right format, at the right time and with the right impact.

2 DISSEMINATION PROCEDURE

Based on the Grant agreement of the project, ICARUS data, as well as all project reports and consortium meetings, are by default confidential for their further industrial exploitation. Rules of protection and publication: GA - Chapter 4 / Subsection 3 - Articles 26 to 31.

2.1 GENERAL RULE

Any scientific publication or information about emerging protectable results should be put available to the consortium on the project SharePoint 45 days before planned publication.

All the partners have 30 days to disapprove (or approve) the data or partial data envisaged to publish. In the absence of any objection within the 30-day period, it is deemed that the parties agree. If an objection is raised within the 30-day period, the affected parties shall seek in good faith a solution on a timely basis.

2.2 PROCEDURE FOR PARTNERS: SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION OR PATENT

Based on Article 8 of the Consortium Agreement, the case of scientific publication or in case of emerging protectable results (patents, trademarks, utility models...):

For conference abstracts, non-published presentations (ppt), delays are shorter:
21 days prior to the deadline
review: 15 days

Step 1: Primary Author send to Dissemination Manager the proposed publications (including mandatory acknowledgement) at least 45 calendar days before the submission (21 days for abstracts and presentations):

- 📎 Date of publication and submission, journal name
- 📎 Date, title and location of the actual event
- 📎 Names and affiliations of all the co-authors
- 📎 Any other relevant information

Step 2: Dissemination Manager uploads the draft on the collaborative platform. Any objection shall be made to the Dissemination Manager, Support to Project Management and Primary Author within 30 calendar days (15 days for abstracts and presentations) after receipt of the publication.

The objecting Party can request a publication delay of not more than 90 calendars days from the time it raised such an objection. After 90 calendars day, the publication is permitted, provided that Confidential Information of the objecting Party has been removed from the publication as indicated by the objecting Party.

Step 3: Once reviewed, the primary author submits the final version to the Dissemination Manager

Final version of publications is stored onto the collaborative platform

Final version numbering

Step 4: The Dissemination Manager updates the ICARUS Activity Report and the platform every 6 months

Step 5: The Dissemination Manager informs INEA Communication Officer of any relevant dissemination activities. A list of actual publications will be included in the public website.

Please note that a publication and/or a breach of confidentiality can destroy the protection of an invention.

3 COMMUNICATION PLAN

3.1 PROJECT NEEDS DEFINITION

The main strategic objectives of the external communication and dissemination plan is to make ICARUS known and to communicate about the project results. The communication and dissemination activities will maximize the promotion of the project and its impact.

The communication strategy aims at:

- Disseminating information regarding the opportunities and advantages reached during the project
- Gathering useful feedbacks from all the stakeholders (researchers, industries, industrial associations, standardization bodies and committees, other running projects and so on)
- Organizing workshops and webinars to be integrated in existing university level teaching programs in the domain of recycling
- Promoting to wide public audience best available and novel technologies for recycling with benefits for citizens and information about the whole value chain to support the public acceptance of the solution.

These activities are essential to maximize the impact of the research, transfer knowledge and results and demonstrate how EU funding contributes to tackle societal challenges.

Communicating ICARUS actions and results is an integral part of the H2020 Grant Agreement (Article 38.1.1) and is essential to maximize the impact of the research, transfer knowledge and results and demonstrate how EU funding contributes to tackle societal challenges. However, it is expected that ICARUS will generate data for further industrial exploitation (Please refer to the D7.14 Data Management Plan for further details). Therefore, considerable care is required to ensure that the project meets both Horizon 2020's communication activities as well as the necessary protections required to maintain intellectual property rights.

3.2 STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION

Identifying stakeholders is the process of targeting groups and organizations for ICARUS communication measures.

The stakeholder inventory will be continuously updated during the project’s lifetime. In previous experience, such stakeholder analysis has proven extremely useful for an adequate, effective and efficient involvement of the wider stakeholder group, both for targeted communication and communication actions, as well as exploitation strategy development.

The methodology of communication/dissemination will rely on influence and interest of the stakeholders (Figure 1) and each category will have its own communication/dissemination strategy.

Figure 1 : Stakeholder mapping

3.3 PROJECT IDENTITY

The ICARUS visual identity has been defined. This visual identity aims to convey the purpose of the project, its spirit and ambitions and facilitate identification of the project. You can see below the project logo in Figure 2).

Figure 2: ICARUS project logo

3.4 MAIN COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

To reach the stakeholders mentioned above, the consortium will rely on different channels. Table 1 **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** presents the targeted audiences for the use of each channel.

Table 1 : ICARUS targeted audience for each channel

Channels	Targeted audiences			
	Potential defenders / disseminators	Potential users	Technical and scientific experts	Citizens / students
Online channels				
Website	X	X	X	X
Social media	X	X	X	X
Newsletter	X	X	X	X
Offline channels				
Conferences, <u>invited</u> seminars and workshops	X	X	X	
Technical and demonstration workshops	X	X	X	X
Journal publications	X	X	X	X

4 ONLINE CHANNELS

The online communication tools already set up by AYMING (BENKEI).

The project public website has been created, including non-confidential information on the project background and goals. It will regularly be updated with project results and agenda. The project public website is operational since September 2021. The deliverable D8.7 present with more details the website organization and content.

An ICARUS LinkedIn profile has been created by AYMING (BENKEI) (Figure 4) at the following address: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/icarus-easme> is operational since September 2021. The number of followers on LinkedIn will be monitor every 6 months.

A newsletter with project presentation and objectives could be released in the coming months.

Figure 3: ICARUS homepage website

PROCESSING AND REFINING OF SECONDARY RAW MATERIALS

ICARUS EASME
Processing and refining of secondary raw materials
Industrie composants électriques/électroniques · Trondheim · 11 abonnés

+ Suivre Voir le site web Plus

Accueil Infos Posts Offres d'emploi Personnes

Infos

ICARUS is a European project, which will secure this process to foster European growth on downstream value chains. This will be done by turning the upstream process wastes, rich in highly pure Si and energy-dense, into a secondary raw material.

voir plus

Voir tous les détails

Posts de la page ...

Figure 4: LinkedIn page

4.1 CONFERENCES, INVITED SEMINARS AND WORKSHOPS

The dissemination of the ICARUS project will be maximized through regular participation to dedicated conferences and workshops. It is expected that results will be presented at least at 2 international events per year over the entire duration of the project.

Table 3: List of conferences/events scheduled for the project

Partner	Conference/Journal/workshop	Year
SINTEF, Granges	2 Conference presentations (TMS, ICASP),	2022, 2024
SINTEF, Granges	2 Journal papers (International Journal of Cast Metal Research, Met. Trans. A)	2021, 2023
SINTEF	Intersolar Conference, Mumbai (India)	2022
SINTEF	3 Conference presentations and papers (EUPVSEC)	2021, 2022, 2023
SINTEF	2 publications in PV Magazin/PV Tech/PV International	2022, 2023
RESITEC	3 Conference presentations and papers (EUPVSEC, EUROPM)	2022, 2023, 2024
SINTEF, CIDETEC	Conference presentation (International Meeting on Lithium Batteries)	2022, 2024
IPG, ROSI	4 Conference presentations (TMS, CSSC, PVSEC)	2022,2024
IPG, ROSI	10 Journal papers (Met. Trans. A, Met. Trans. B, Mat.Chem.&Phys., J. Cryst. Growth)	2022,2023,2024
IPG, ROSI	2 PhDs	2023
ROSI	3 patents: 1. Silicon powder feeding technology for micro-metric powder. 2. Conditioning of melted recycled silicon. 3. Coolant recycling from wafer sawing	2021-2024
IPG	1 patent on efficient removal of carbon and oxygen impurities from Si-kerf	2021-2023
UCY	At least 8 Conference presentations (Materials Research Society (MRS, E-MRS), International/European Thermoelectric Society Conferences, CIMTEC, TMS)	2021-2024
UCY	At least 6 Journal papers (Journal of Alloys and Compounds, Acta Materialia, Advanced Materials, etc)	2021-2024
UCY	Patent on the fabrication of thermoelectric silicides and modules based on Si-kerf starting materials.	2024
BIFA	2 conference papers (EUPVSEC)	2022, 2024
BIFA	2 workshops and with publication of outcome on webpage	2022, 2024
CEA	1 Conference presentation (PVSEC)	2023
CEA	1 Journal paper (Journal of Applied Physics)	2023
CEA	1 patent on improved diamond wire sawing technology for reduced impurity contamination of the Si-kerf	2021-2023
MMEX	3 Presentations at conferences on thermoelectrics (ECT, ICT, other)	2022, 2023, 2024
MMEX	Presentation at workshop/techday with Car Manufacturers (to be defined)	2023

Every 6 months at the General Assembly the WP8 leader is establishing the list of future events in which the ICARUS partners will represent ICARUS consortium. ICARUS partners are also invited to provide the WP8 members with some communication elements (picture, brief note) in order to communicate on the social media about the ICARUS participation to the event.

4.2 TECHNICAL AND DEMONSTRATION WORKSHOPS

ICARUS will organize two workshops during its lifetime (BIFA, CHEMCON, AYMING (BENKEI)).

- A Stakeholder workshop “Secondary Materials” SM1 (M36)
- A Stakeholder workshop “Secondary Materials” SM2 (M42).

4.3 JOURNAL PUBLICATIONS

ICARUS will follow an open and active publication policy through peer-reviewed in scientific journals. The publications will be made available Open Access by using both the Green and the Golden Route. As for the Green route, the publications will be made available through the institutional repositories of each Partner of the Consortium and on the website of ICARUS. As for the Golden route, the publications will be made available Open Access directly at the Publisher. A publication fee is required in this case (for most of the Publishers) and this will be covered by the Author Institutions. We expect an average of 2 papers written by each task leading institution as first authors, by the end of the project.

Table 4: Targeted Journals for publications

Partner	Publications in high-impact journals and open access
SINTEF, GRANGES	2 Journal papers (International Journal of Cast Metal Research, Met. Trans. A)
SINTEF	3 Conference presentations and papers (EUPVSEC)
SINTEF	2 publications in PV Magazin/PV Tech/PV International
RESITEC	3 Conference presentations and papers (EUPVSEC, EUROPM)
IPG, ROSI	10 Journal papers (Met. Trans. A, Met. Trans. B, Mat.Chem.&Phys., J. Cryst. Growth)
UCY	At least 6 Journal papers (Journal of Alloys and Compounds, Acta Materialia, Advanced Materials, etc)
BIFA	2 conference papers (EUPVSEC)
CEA	1 Journal paper (Journal of Applied Physics)
MMEX	3 Presentations at conferences on thermoelectrics (ECT, ICT, other)

5 MONITORING AND EVALUATION PLAN

Communication and dissemination activities will be regularly monitored during the project lifetime to assess the effectiveness of the activities realized and implement changes if necessary.

For this purpose, several Key Performance Indicators (KPI) have been defined with target numbers (Table55).

Table5: WP8 Key Performance Indicators

Dissemination channels	KPI
LinkedIn followers	At least 400 LinkedIn followers by the end of the project
Communication / Dissemination activities	At least 10 Communication / Dissemination activities per year
Publications	At least 10 scientific publications in open access in peer-reviewed journals
Website performance	At least 4 000 Views on the website at the end of the project

These KPI will be followed on a six-month basis and the table below presents the assessment summary since the beginning of the project:

Table 6: Key Performance Indicators –assessment

Dissemination channels	KPI -Target	M18	M36	M48	M6 Assessment
LinkedIn followers	Number of Linked In contacts	100	200	400	
Communication / Dissemination activities	Number of Communication / Dissemination activities	at least 10 per year	at least 10 per year	at least 10 per year	
Publications	Number of Publications	at least 5 per year	at least 5 per year	at least 5 per year	
Website performance	Views on the website	1500	3000	4000	

6 ALLOCATED RESOURCES

The Table 7 presents allocated resources to the communication and dissemination activities (Task 7).

Table 7: Partners effort for Task 7.3 communication and dissemination activities

	Partner	PM
1	SINTEF	6
2	NOSI	1
3	RESITEC	2
4	NORSUN	2
5	ROSI	2
6	IPG	2
7	CEA	0,5
9	BIFA	2
10	CIDETEC	1
11	UNIV. CYPRUS	1
12	MMEX	2
13	GRANGES	0,5
14	SGL	2
15	CHEMCON	5
16	BENKEI	9
17	FIVEN	1
	Total	40

